

LEXICAL FEATURES OF COMPOUND WORDS IN KARAKALPAK, ENGLISH AND GERMAN

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Annotation. *This article deals with the following issues: the lexical features of compound words in three languages: Karakalpak, English and German, their typological analysis and comparison. In the article similarities and differences of the compounds in Karakalpak, English and German are identified from lexical point of view.*

Keywords: *Compound words (CW), word formation, lexical features, lexical point of view, lexicon, correlation, semantic connection, Komposition.*

Composition is one of most productive ways of word formation in Turkic as well as in Germanic languages. The compound words in Karakalpak, English and German languages have some common features. However, there exist differences between them as well, as they are from grammatical point of view, differently structured.

In modern linguistic literature, there is mainly used the term “word formation” in the questions related to word building. By the term of word formation linguists understand formation of new words by means of various word building models in a particular language in a particular period of time. The basic types of word formation are derivation and compounding. Word formation is, on the one hand, closely related to lexicon and, on the other hand, to grammar. The relation between word formation and lexicon is that every new word in the language becomes a unit of the vocabulary of the language. And the relation between word formation and grammar is that every new word in the language is included to the lexical and grammatical category called a part of speech.

Word composition is a common type of word formation, that is made by connecting two or more elements into one unit. The way of word building is counted to be one of the most ancient in Karakalpak, English and German languages. The basic way of joining components of the compounds into one whole is to connect stems of different parts of speech without any changes or with some modifications. And this means of composition is widespread in the languages investigated.

As it was mentioned above, according to A. Bekbergenov in Karakalpak language compound words are classified into: a) composite words; b) paired words; c) paired-repeated words; d) fused words; e) abbreviated words/shortenings.

Consequently, compound words make more than half of the whole lexicon of Karakalpak language. Furthermore, compounds can belong to any part of speech from morphological point of view.

If to compare compound words in Karakalpak with the ones in English and in German, it is worthwhile to note that Karakalpak language is richer than English and German languages. Now that Karakalpak compounds are divided into 5 subclasses, they make more than half of the vocabulary of the language, whereas in English they are subdivided into 3 types (Arnold,1986,123), and in German – into 4 subtypes.

In English and German there don't exist paired and paired-repeated compounds, while they make a huge part of the spoken and written language in Karakalpak. As for the abbreviated compound words in Karakalpak, the group of words is considered to be a separate type of word formation in English and German languages. I.V. Arnold states that "...Shortening, on the other hand, may be represented as significant subtraction, in which part of the original word or word group is taken away. Moreover, every kind of shortening differs from derivation, composition and conversion in being not a new arrangement of existing morphemes, but often a source of new ones. As a type of word-building shortening of spoken words, also called clipping or curtailment is recorded in the English language as far back as the 15th century." Thus, Arnold refers shortenings/abbreviated words to a separate type of word formation. Apart from that German linguists also find the word formation means relatively new and exceptional.

I.G. Olshanskiy and A.E.Guseva admit that "Kurzwortbildung ist eine relativ neue und außerordentlich produktive Wortbildungsart. Diese Art der Wortbildung entsteht durch die Verkürzung eines längeren Wortes oder mehrerer Ausgangswörter (eines Kompositums: *Lastkraftwagen* – LKW, einer Wortverbindung: *elektronische Datenverarbeitung* – EDV)."

However, there is also another point in the classification of the compound words of the three languages. Namely there exist a group of compounds in English and German formed in the result of two linguistic phenomena: derivation and compounding.

Such compounds are called "derivational compounds" ('*Zusammenbildungen*' in German). Derivational compounds or compound-derivatives are the words in which the structural integrity of two free stems is ensured by a suffix referring to the combination as a whole, not to one of its elements: *kind-hearted*, *old-timer*, *schoolboyishness*, *teenager*. In the coining of the derivational compounds two types of word formation are at work¹. Accordingly, Arnold refers the group of words to compounds by emphasizing their structural features identical with compound words.

Among the German compounds a special role plays so called 'Zusammenbildungen', equivalent to derivational compounds in English. In the formation of *Zusammenbildungen* two processes take place: derivation (Derivation) and composition (Komposition). For instance, *Schuh/mach/er*, *Früh/aufsteh/er*, *Wichtig/tu/er*, *zwei/stuf/ig*. Here the 'Frühaufsteher' is made up of 'früh', 'aufstehen' and the suffix 'er'. The suffix helps to combine the words and to have the single lexical meaning. However, such type of compounds do not exist in Karakalpak language. Even though there are compound words, especially compound adjectives in Karakalpak that have similar structural features as the derivational compounds in English and German, such compounds are referred to composite words. In other words, compound words formed in result of derivation and compounding as the followings *uzin boy/li* (*tall*), *ko'k ko'z/li* (*blue-eyed*), *qara qas/li* (*with black eyebrows*), *sari shash/li* (*fair haired*), *aq saqal/li* (*with a white beard*) can be categorized as composite adjectives. In the above given word 'qara qas/li' is made up of 'qara' (black), 'qas' (eyebrow) and the suffix '-li'. The suffix serves as a morphological unit which helps to connect words as grammatically and lexically. According to Bekbergenov, such composite adjectives are productive in modern Karakalpak.

¹ I.V. Arnold „The English Word”, М: Высшая школа, 1986, p 128

The first component of compound adjectives of this type can be any part of speech including noun, adjective, pronoun and a numeral, the second component is always an adjective with the suffixes *-li/li*, *-siz/-siz*, *-liq/-lik*. For ex: *qoy ko'z/li*, *iyt minez/li*, *adam ta'riz/li*, *eki ju'z/li*, *on etaj/li*, *pu'tkil soyuz/liq*, *aq shash/li* and so on.

Besides in Karakalpak there are compound adjectives in which the first component is usually a noun (sometimes an adjective or adverb), the second constituent is a verbal adjective with the suffix *-ar/-er/-r* (and their negative forms): *toy tarqat/ar*, *qan ish/er*, *is jaq/pas*, *qos jaq/pas*, *jan ku'y/er*, *aq pis/er*, *kesh pis/er*. The compound 'toy tarqatar' here is made up of 'toy' (noun stem, the first component), 'tarqat' (verbal stem, the second component), '-ar' (the suffix). The morphological structure of compound adjective is the following: noun + verbal adjective + (-er). A. Bekbergenov admits that they belong to composite compounds. The compound 'kesh piser' is also made up of 'kesh' which is an adverb, the verbal stem 'pisiw' together with the suffix -er forms the verbal adjective 'piser'.

If to compare the same word building model with the ones in English, it turns out that such compounds are categorized as compound-derivatives in English, as it has been mentioned above, while they are referred to composite compounds in Karakalpak.

The most widespread of the morphological structures that often can be found in all three languages is noun + noun structure. This type is considered to be numerous and unlimited in number, as well as the oldest word building model especially in English and German languages.

Apart from that Ginzburg also states that correlation is a regular interaction and interdependence of compounds and certain types of free phrases which conditions both the potential possibility of appearance of compound words and their structure and semantic type. Thus, the fact that there is a potential possibility of individual phrases with the underlying pattern, for ex, as A + as N in as white as snow, as white as blood presupposes a potential possibility of compound words of the n+a type like *snow-white*, *blood-red* etc, with their structure and meaning relation of the components preconditioned. It happens that in this particular case compound adjectives are more typical and preferred as a language means of conveying the quality based on comparison.

Structural and semantic correlation by no means implies identity or a one-to-one correspondence of each individual pattern of compound "words to one phrase pattern.

For example, the n + nv type of compound nouns comprises different patterns, such as [n + (v + -er)] – *rocket-flyer*, *shoe-maker*, *bottle-opener*; [n + (v + -ing)] – *rocket-flying*, *football-playing*; [n + (v + -ion)] – *price-education*. All these patterns differing in the individual suffix used in the final analysis correlate with verbal-nominal word-groups of the V+N type (e.g. to fly rockets), the meaning of the active doer (*rocket-flyer*) or the action (*rocket-flying*) is conveyed by the suffixes. However, the reverse relationship is not uncommon, e.g. one derivational pattern of compound adjectives (n + a) in words like *oil-rich*, *sky-high*, *grass-green* corresponds to a variety of word-group patterns which differ in the grammatical and semantic relationship between member-words expressed in phrases by different prepositions. Thus, compound adjectives of this type may correspond to phrase patterns A + of + N, e.g. *pleasure-tired*; A+in +N, e.g. *oil-rich*; as A as N, e.g. *grass-green*.

Another example of the same type of correlation of the semantic relations underlying word-groups of the N + prp + N type, such as relations of resemblance (e.g. needle-fish), local and temporal relations (e.g. *country-house*, *night-flight*), relations purpose (e.g. *search-warrant*), etc. which in word-groups are conveyed by prepositions or other functions words.

Compound words, due to the fact they do not require any explicit way to convey the semantic relationship between their components except their order, are of much wider range, leave more freedom for semantic interpretation and convey meaning in a more compressed and concise way. This makes the meaning of compounds more flexible and situationally derived. It follows that motivation and regularity of semantic and structural correlation with free word-groups are the basic factors favouring a high degree of productivity of composition and may be used to set rules guiding spontaneous, analogic formation of new compound words. It is natural that those types of compound words which do not establish such regular correlations and that are marked by a lack or very low degree of motivation must be regarded as unproductive as, for example, compound nouns of the a+n type, e.g. *bluebell*, *blackbird*, *mad-doctor*.

Another lexical feature of compounds (fused words) in Karakalpak is that the components of the words can be delexicalized, namely lose their primary meaning and only in combination they give another new meaning. The components of such compounds have been used together and become inseparable. The connection of the two elements gives new lexical meaning and consequently forms new compound word. For ex: *atqulaq*, *buzawbas*, *tasbaqa*, *Qon'irat*, *Qizketken*, *Xojeli*, *ku'nko'ris*, *besbarmaq*, *segizko'z*, *aqsaqal*, *aqsu'yek*, *aqbilek*, *ko'zashiq* and so on. The compound word *atqulaq* consists of two components "at" (horse), *qulaq* "ear", together translated as "horse ear". However, this is the name of the plant that is like the horse's ear on its shape. The next word *Qon'irat* is also made up of two elements: "qon'ir" (brown) and "at" (horse). But their combination gives the name of the city. The other example *aqsaqal* is formed from the components "aq" (white) and "saqal" (beard), together translated as white beard. However, in Karakalpak language the compound is used while addressing to a man who is much older or if we mean a male person who is high level official.

Such type of words can also be found among composite words: *ko'k bet*, *ayaq kiyim*, *tas bawir*, *iyt ayaq*, *suw jilan*, *tu'ye taban* etc.

If to compare above stated Karakalpak compounds with the English compounds, it is worthwhile to note that in English there are also compound words whose components have lost their literal meaning and in connection with the second word forms a new meaning. For instance, *blackboard*, *blacklist*, *bluebottle*, *blackbird* etc. In these example 'blackboard' does not denote the board that is of black colour, but the teaching aid used in the classroom. The word 'blacklist' means lexically not the list that is black, but the list of the names of people, companies, products or countries that an organization or a government considers unacceptable and that must be avoided. Such phenomena can also be observed in German compounds: *Weisswein*, *Mutterliebe*. Here the compound 'Weisswein' is translated as 'white wine', however it is not white and just a sort of wine, that is almost colourless. The word 'Mutterliebe' is made up of words 'Mutter'(mother) and 'Liebe' (love). But the word lexically means not the love of a particular mother, it denotes the feeling of motherhood in general.

Conclusion

From the comparison of the above made, it can be concluded that compound words in each language investigated, have both similarities and differences. English and German compounds contain a subgroup of words 'bahuvrihi', compounds metonymically and metaphorically denote a person or thing. While such words are referred to phraseological units in Karakalpak language. The similarity between the compounds of the languages explored is the delexicalization of the components of compounds in each language. From the typological analysis of the compounds in Karakalpak, English and German languages and the examples given above we can infer that they represent similar lexical features.

Moreover, compound words in German contain so called 'Zusammenrückungen', a separate group of words 'imperative nouns', that exist in English in limited number as well. However, imperative nouns do not exist in the Karakalpak language.

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